

MEASUREMENT OF RESIDUAL STRESS IN A356/SiC_p METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE BY NANOINDENTATION

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1 Introduction

Metal matrix composites(MMCs) have been used as structural materials due to their outstanding specific performances which other materials don't have. However, they generally become weak when exposed to a repetitive thermal shock, which produce residual stress by the inconsistency of the thermal expansion coefficients (CTE) of matrix and reinforcement materials. Residual stress in composite materials can greatly affect on the dynamic mechanical behavior, therefore, the residual stress measurement is very important issue before applying them into structures. To measure the residual stress, cutting and hole-drilling test, X-ray diffraction (XRD), neutron diffraction and ultrasound methods are conventionally used [1].

In this study, residual stress on matrix of A356/20vol.-%-SiC_p MMCs was measured and its variation by aging conditions was investigated. Nanoindentation method was chosen for residual stress measurement because its infinitesimal region with target position makes it possible to perform the test only on the matrix. The specimens were heat-treated at different aging temperatures (154, 200, 250°C) to generate various residual stress states, where 154°C is the critical aging temperature of A356 [2]. The nanoindentation results were compared with those of conventional XRD method to validate the nanoindentation method.

2 Theory

2.1 Nanoindentation

For materials with tensile residual stress, smaller load is required for the indentation than materials without residual stress. On the contrary, larger load is required when compressive residual stress exists. As a result, the load-displacement curve (P-h curve) moves up by compressive residual stress and down by tensile residual stress state (see Fig.1) [3].

According to the previous studies, residual stress can be calculated by comparing two P-h curves of specimens with and without residual stress. Lee and

Kwon reported that residual stress directly affects the indentation load under the same depth of penetration [4, 5]. They calculated the residual stress from the difference between maximum loads of stressed and stress-free samples with equations for equi-biaxial residual stress states

$$L_R = -\frac{2}{3}\sigma_R A_C \quad (1)$$

and for general residual stress states

$$L_R = \frac{-(1+\kappa)}{3}\sigma_R^x A_C \quad (2)$$

where L_R is difference of maximum loads, σ_R is residual stress, κ is stress ratio, i.e. $\sigma_R^y = \kappa\sigma_R^x$ and A_C is contact area between indenter and material. The contact area is estimated by

$$A_C = 24.5h_c^2 \quad (3)$$

for the ideal Berkovich indenter tip where h_c is penetration depth [6].

2.2 X-ray diffraction

When X-ray is injected on metallic material surface, it is scattered and makes a diffraction pattern according to the disordered crystal lattice orientation. The residual stress in materials can vary the diffraction pattern by changing the distance of lattice plane.

Fig.1. Variation of P-h curve by residual stress

In this study, residual stress was measured by the $\sin^2\psi$ method which uses the slope of straight line between reflection angle (2θ) and $\sin^2\psi$. Residual stress is calculated by following equation.

$$\sigma = \frac{-E}{2(1+\nu)} \cot\theta \frac{\partial 2\theta}{\partial \sin^2\psi} \quad (4)$$

where E is Young's modulus, ν is Poisson's ratio, and σ is residual stress. The term $\partial 2\theta / \partial \sin^2\psi$ is the slope of $2\theta - \sin^2\psi$ line. Positive slope makes σ to have negative sign which means compressive residual stress. Negative slope corresponds to tensile residual stress state [7, 8].

3 Materials and experiment procedure

3.1 Materials

SiC particle reinforced A356 matrix composites of MC-21[®] was tested and Fig.2 is the microstructure of MMCs. Nanoindentation test was done for four samples which were all solution-heat-treated at 540°C for 8 hours and then aged differently; 1) without aging, 2) aging at 154°C for 4 hours, 3) aging at 200°C and 4) aging at 250°C.

The free-stress samples as a reference were prepared by heat-treating the squeeze-casted A356 alloy in same conditions of MMCs. All the samples were mechanically polished by emery papers and diamond suspension, and then finished by electrolytic polishing at 10V for 20 seconds.

3.2 Experiment

Nanoindentation test was conducted by Nano indenter XP of MTS[™] with 'XP Basic hardness, Modulus at a depth' mode. Indenter tip was Berkovich type and the limit depth was set to 500nm. Indentation test was done more than 50 times for each sample.

Fig.2. SEM image of A356/20%vol.-SiCp MMCs

The representative results were selected for the comparisons between MMCs and matrix alloy for four different aging conditions. XRD was tested with Co-K α X-ray at the condition of 148.7 diffraction angle and 0.02 step size.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Nanoindentation

Fig.3 and Fig.4 show P-h curves for different aging conditions and residual stress of MMCs obtained from those curves respectively. Residual stress is calculated using the difference of maximum loads in P-h curves by Eq (1) because the isotropic behavior of particle reinforced MMCs would generate equibiaxial residual stress states.

For all cases, P-h curve of A356 matrix alloy places upper than that of MMCs, which implies that MMCs are under tensile residual stress state regardless of aging conditions. Both the samples without aging and aged at 154°C show similar residual stress of 168MPa (Fig.3a and 3b), while it decreases near to 100MPa for the samples aged at 200°C and at 250°C.

Hardness at maximum displacement is plotted in Fig.5. In both A356 alloy and MMCs, hardness slightly increases, and then stiffly decreases according to the increase of aging temperature. This result corresponds to the well-known behavior of the aging heat treatment. The initial increase implies the critically-aged state and the latter decrease attributes to the over aging condition.

4.2 XRD result

Fig.6 and Fig.7 are $\sin^2\psi - 2\theta$ graph by XRD test and residual stress of MMCs respectively. Residual stress is calculated using the slope of linear fitting line by Eq (4).

Residual stress of non-aged sample is compressive, while all the aging-treated samples show tensile stress state. The magnitude of tensile residual stress decreases as the increase of aging temperature, and becomes almost zero at aging temperature of 250°C.

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Fig.3. P-h curve by nanoindentation

Fig.4. Residual stress of MMCs by nanoindentation

Fig.6. $\sin^2\psi - 2\theta$ graph by XRD test

Fig.5. Hardness at maximum displacement

Fig.7. Residual stress of MMCs by XRD test

4.3 Comparison of two methods

Fig. 8 shows the values of residual stress for both methods. In the sample without aging, the result gives opposite residual stress state, tensile state in nanoindentation and compressive in XRD method. This may attribute to the different scale of measurement target, and further research should be done to investigate it. The aging-treated specimens show similar tendency even though the values are quite different. Residual stress increases up to maximum value at peak aging condition (154°C), and then decreases continuously at over aging conditions (200 ~ 250°C). To explain the difference of residual stress values between two methods, two points can be considered. One is that the surface of MMCs is so irregular with reinforcements that the test results would have strong regional dependency. The other is how to prepare the stress-free samples. In this study, they were chosen by A356 which were heat-treated at the same condition with MMCs. However, it is well-known that reinforcements in MMCs influences precipitation and dislocation structure at the adjacent region to interfaces [9, 10]. As a result, different heat treatment can produce the difference not only in the level of residual stress but also in the microstructure with dislocations and precipitations.

5 Conclusion

In this study, residual stress on matrix region of A356/20vol.%-SiC_p MMCs was measured by nanoindentation and XRD methods and its variation by aging conditions was investigated.

- Residual stress measured by nanoindentation shows a similar behavior to that by XRD method. Residual stress increases as the increase of aging temperature until peak aging condition, and then decreases continuously in over aging region.

Fig.8. Residual stress of MMCs by both methods

- The values of residual stress are quite different between two test methods. This may attribute not only to the scale difference of measuring target but also to the different microstructure affected by aging treatment. Moreover, careful consideration of sample surfaces should be needed to validate the measuring accuracy of nanoindentation method.

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